

NEW COMBINATIONS IN *SPOROBOLUS* (POACEAE: CHLORIDOIDEAE)

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ABSTRACT

The following four new combinations are made: ***Sporobolus borszczowii*** (Regel) P.M. Peterson, ***Sporobolus borszczowii*** subsp. ***acuminatus*** (Trin.) P.M. Peterson, ***Sporobolus borszczowii*** subsp. ***ambiguus*** (Boiss. & Balansa ex Boiss.) P.M. Peterson, and ***Sporobolus montevidensis*** (Arechav.) P.M. Peterson & Saarela.

Sporobolus R. Br. is a worldwide genus of more than 230 species, nearly equally distributed between the Western and Eastern hemispheres, and is found in tropical to temperate regions throughout the world (Clayton et al. 2006; Peterson et al. 2014a; Simon 2014). A recent molecular phylogeny and subgeneric treatment expanding the circumscription of *Sporobolus* R. Br. was published with a conservation proposal (2332) to incorporate the species of *Calamovilfa* (A. Gray) Hack. ex Scribn. & Southw., *Crypsis* Aiton, *Spartina* Schreb., and *Thellungia* Stapf within *Sporobolus* (Peterson et al. 2014a, b). In Peterson et al. (2014a), *Trachynotia cynosuroides* (L.) Michx. was cited in synonymy twice — mistakenly included as a homotypic synonym of *Sporobolus michauxianus* (Hitc.) P.M. Peterson & Saarela and correctly included as a homotypic synonym of *Sporobolus cynosuroides* (L.) P.M. Peterson & Saarela. In the same publication (Peterson et al. 2014a), a new combination in *Sporobolus* for *Crypsis borszczowii* Regel was not effectively made, consequently two subspecies were invalid, and an earlier publication [*Sporobolus densiflorus* (E. Fourn.) Vasey] was pointed out by Kanchi Gandhi, which made our combination based on *Spartina densiflorus* Brongn. a later homonym (Peterson et al. 2014a). In order to correct these mistakes we make four new combinations in *Sporobolus*.

SPOROBOLUS BORSZCZOWII (Regel) P.M. Peterson, **comb. nov.** Basionym: *Crypsis borszczowii* Regel, Bull. Soc. Imp. Naturalistes Moscou 41(2): 306. 1868. *Heleochloa borszczowii* (Regel) Roshev. ex B. Fedtsch., Izv. Imp. Bot. Sada Petra Velikago 14 (Suppl. 2): 52. 1914. *Crypsis acuminata* subsp. *borszczowii* (Regel) Kit Tan, Fl. Turkey & E. Aegean Isl. 9: 584. 1985. **TYPE. KAZAKHSTAN.** Deserto Aralo-Caspium, Ust Ürt [now Kazakhstan or adjacent Uzbekistan], 25 Sep 1857, *E. Boresczow 500* (holotype: LE; isotype: K barcode 000907273 [image!]).

SPOROBOLUS BORSZCZOWII subsp. **ACUMINATUS** (Trin.) P.M. Peterson, **comb. nov. & stat. nov.** Basionym: *Crypsis acuminata* Trin., Neue Entd. 2: 57. 1821. **TYPE. KAZAKHSTAN.** Lower reaches of the Ural River (lectotype [designated by Tsvelev in Federov, Zlaki SSSR, Grasses of the Soviet Union: 647, 1776]: LE TRIN 1523B1!).

SPOROBOLUS BORSZCZOWII subsp. **AMBIGUUS** (Boiss. & Balansa ex Boiss.) P.M. Peterson, **comb. nov.** Basionym: *Heleochloa ambigua* Boiss. & Balansa ex Boiss., Fl. Orient. 5: 477. 1884 *Crypsis ambigua* (Boiss. & Balansa ex Boiss.) Lorch in Bull. Res. Council Israel, Sect. D, Bot. 11: 97. 1962. *Crypsis acuminata* subsp. *ambigua* (Boiss. & Balansa ex Boiss.) Kit Tan, Fl. Turkey & E. Aegean Isl. 9: 584. 1985. **TYPE. TURKEY.** İzmir, Station de Boudja, près de Smyrne, 150 m, 31 Aug 1866, *B. Balansa 1541* (lectotype [designated by Peterson et al., Taxon 63: 1234. 2014]: W barcode 0027063 [image!]; isolectotype: W barcode 0048400 [image!]).

SPOROBOLUS MONTEVIDENSIS (Arechav.) P.M. Peterson & Saarela, **comb. nov.** Basionym: *Spartina montevidensis* Arechav., Anales Mus. Nac. Montevideo 1(5): 378–380, t. 43. 1896. **TYPE. URUGUAY.** Montevideo, “Vive en las orillas del Río de la Plata, en parajes cenagosos ordinariamente. Florece en los meses de Febrero y Marzo.” 1884, *J. Arechaveleta s.n.* (holotype: MVM; isotypes: Real Colegio Alfonso XII [RCAXII] 2425, W barcode 1916-0030779 ex herb. Hackel [image!], WIS barcode 0254293 [image!]).

Spartina densiflora Brongn., Voy. Monde 2(2): 14. 1829. *Chauvinia chilensis* Steud., Syn. Pl. Glumac. 1: 362. 1854, nom. illeg. superfl. *Sporobolus densiflorus* (Brongn.) P.M. Peterson & Saarela, Taxon 63: 1237. 2014, nom. illeg. hom., non *Sporobolus densiflorus* (E. Fourn.) Vasey, Enum. Pl. Guatem. 1: 52. 1889.

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